

Only an empty pedestal has remained. Antiquity and war trauma in Zbigniew Herbert's "Chord of light"

Introduction

Zbigniew Herbert is one of the most important Polish poets, essayists, and drama writers of 20th century, widely known outside Poland as well, mostly from his book of essays *Barbarian in the Garden* and poems about Mr. Cogito. Another trademark of his poetry is the use of classical mythology, philosophical concepts, and historical figures outside their typical convention.

Interestingly, Herbert decided to make his literary debut – the poetry book called “Chord of light” – very late in his life, at the age of 32, in 1956. This was facilitated by the temporarily improved political and cultural situation in post-war Poland after the death of Stalin. Because of his connections to anti-government opposition, he was not allowed to publish an original poetry book, although he actively wrote poems during and right after the Second World War. That is the reason why critics most often compared his debut to the works of poets that first published in the late 40s¹. Another aspect was the poet’s willingness to address the experience of the past war.

Herbert carefully selected poems for his official debut. Moreover, as Mateusz Antoniuk remarks, the poems were arranged in a chronological order, which is an uncommon practice for Herbert, and represents the poet’s path to the debut². The only exception from that pattern is the final poem, “Arion”, but, given the overall message of this work, it fits in perfectly as the epilogue of the entire book. We will be analyzing this interesting piece later. The book comprises 39 poems in total; 21 of them contain classical themes or at least small allusions. The most important motifs include: the downfall of the world created on ancient values and perspectives; ancient figures, and places as representations of certain ideas, confronted with the horrors of war.

¹ Kornhauser 2000: 20-21.

² Antoniuk 2009: 441.

War and ancient tradition. Contrast views on Herbert's poetry.

This short thematical summary of *Chord of Light* might seem puzzling at first. I introduced Herbert as an ardent admirer of classical past, who keenly referenced antiquity in his poems. At the same time, these references do not always sound favorable and positive. This paradox, present at every stage of Herbert's poetry, is the reason why there are so many contradictory critical views on Herbert's attitude toward the traditional classical model of culture that belongs to the past³. Scholars argue whether Herbert in fact was emotionally cold⁴ and built in his works a stagnant catalogue of ruins, ancient figures, and books, that undergoes deformation and irony, and because of that depicts the vulnerability of today's culture⁵. Other critics, in contrast, claim that Herbert is a pure classicist, a poet who repeats archetypical models only to confront the old culture and present experience⁶. Stanisław Barańczak proposes a seemingly reasonable solution to this impasse in his book *A refugee from utopia: the Poetry of Zbigniew Herbert*. The title is very much telling in this context: Barańczak sees Herbert as a poet, for whom the classical past is always an important reference point, but never an idealized, conservative utopia⁷. As he argues: "His poetry is a "tragic vision" reported in a classical style"⁸. The tragedy of his experiences is represented and processed by juxtaposition with the past, filtered through the lens of irony and demasking⁹. At the same time his poetry does not avoid traditional, extensive poetic devices such as metaphor, rhythm, and comparison. In this poetical dimension, "past, present, and future happen together"¹⁰ and allow the reader to peer into Herbert's attempts to understand general history and to find a new place in the post-war world for himself, a man shaped by the old order.

Grieving the past, looking for the future

The mission is not easy given the fact, that the previously known harmony was lost, and the possibility of regaining balance is uncertain. The tragedy of that situation is expressed in the poem *To Apollo*. The Greek god of poetry is the personification of lost values, visions of morality, ethics, and aesthetics shaped based on idealized views of antiquity:

rapt by the sound of his own song

³ Barańczak 2001: 16-19; Popovic 2007: 75.

⁴ Kornhauser 2000: 20.

⁵ Barańczak 2001: 16;

⁶ Idem: 19.

⁷ Idem: 17.

⁸ Idem: 25.

⁹ Antoniuk 2009: 454-455.

¹⁰ Szóstak 2011: 49.

he raised a lyre to the height of silence

immersed in himself
his pupils white as a stream

stone
from his sandals
to the ribbons in his hair

The statue of Apollo becomes a cold, barren, and illusional symbol of the past¹¹, responsible, however, for the subject's vision of the world. The vision now irretrievably lost and grieved:

give me back
youth's shout
arms held out
and my head
in an immense crest of delight

The statue is now shattered, as everything the subject – and with him the poet – believed in. Moreover – the gravity of war was way heavier, than the heroic tradition led him to think:

the epic's fire was different
the city's fire was different

heroes did not return from the expedition
there were no heroes
the unworthy survived

The poem ends with the image of the poet shattered as the statue of Apollo:

I am seeking a statue
drowned in my youth

only an empty pedestal remains—
the trace of a hand seeking a form

In the post-war world, the old balance is nonexistent, but at the same time nothing seems to be capable of replacing it.

¹¹ Popovic 2007: 78-79.

The tragedy of war does not only shatter the intellectual and ideological sphere of human life. It ends real lives of mostly young people. In two poems, similar in general concept and structure, Herbert depicts the cruel death of a nameless soldier, one of many entangled in a fight without hope. The poet could widely draw from his acquaintances with such soldiers, as he was likely engaged in various kinds of resistance movements during the war¹². In both poems the crucial role belongs to the figure of a Greek goddess – subsequently of Athena and of Nike. Unlike Apollo, both symbolize mercy for the young victims and helplessness in the face of fate. The poem addressed to Athena takes on the form of a prayer. The personification of just war is begged to relieve the pain of soldiers fighting for their invaded motherland:

in the empty body
opened by a spear
pour the oil
of gentle radiance

tear from the eyes
the eyelids' scales

let them look

The fight and death, although heroic, is still cruel and not deserved. The subject, in fact, begs for justice for the victims – justice being the exposure of the tragedy and rejection of mythicization of their fate.

The poem addressed to Nike displays the same belief – death in the name of ideas of the higher order is not as glorious as it was presented in literature, but its reality is complex and has a dark, terrifying component¹³:

she understands
that tomorrow at dawn
this boy must be found
with an open breast
closed eyes
and the acid obol of his country
under his numb tongue

¹² Herbert himself reminded of this fact on many occasions, but to this day we lack enough evidence to prove the concrete forms of his wartime resistance activities.

¹³ Kornhauser 2000: 25-26.

The goddess is additionally the symbol of pity towards the young soldier, probably stemming from the author's grief of the death of his colleagues:

that youth will perish soon
right now the scale containing his fate
abruptly falls
toward the earth

Nike would terribly like
to go up
and kiss him on the forehead

(...)

Thus Nike hesitates
and at last decides
to remain in the position
which sculptors taught her
being mightily ashamed of that flash of emotion

This emotional image also symbolizes the helplessness of ancient values in the new kind of ruthless war.

Once more the question becomes an important yet complicated issue for Herbert: the challenges of poetry after the war and the limits of his own artistic expression. How do you speak about the despicable, how can you be a true witness of your own experiences? The ironic representation of his own incapability is a dominant theme of "On Troy". The poem's protagonist: a poet – unknown and unspecified, but instinctively connected with Herbert himself by the reader – attempts to sing about the Troy. The city does not recall its ancient model yet has the characteristic of any Polish city from WWII instead¹⁴: the ravines of former streets and the wind blowing up the red dust. Yet the protagonist attempts to tell the story of a new Troy exactly as the heroic tradition preserved the old Troy:

—how to lead out
people from the ruins
how to lead out
a chorus from a poem

¹⁴ Kornhauser 2000: 23.

thinks a poet perfect
as a pillar of salt

As it turns out, the pathos is not the right tool to express trauma, which transcends the limits of traditional poetry. The poet fails in his attempts because of the gap between literary convention and actual reality:

on a harmonica
a cripple plays a tune
about willows' braids
about a girl

the poet says nothing
rain is coming down

Traditional poetry is speechless and unsuited to the present experiences. Herbert declares this statement once more in the final poem of the collection, "Arion". His ironical demasking of false and unreliable ideals reaches its peak in the depiction of mythical poet from Lesbos:

What Arion is singing about
nobody here could say exactly
the essential thing is that he restores world harmony
(...)

Look how the animals are smiling
People are living on white flowers

The song of Arion restores the Golden Age: nature calms down in the shadow of one hexameter, animals are smiling, the predator brings no harm to the prey, ordinary people forget about their everyday lives. Everything seems so uncritically peaceful and perfect – at least at first. However, was this poetic idyll ever real? The play with the Golden Age motif and the associations of eating flowers with lotus eaters from The *Odyssey* effectively demask the false image of idealized poetry¹⁵. When the dusk comes, Arion tames the dolphin and grotesquely leaves the scene:

How handsome Arion
is —say all the girls—
when he floats out to sea

¹⁵ Popovic 2007: 76-77.

alone

with a garland of horizons on his head

The deceitful, pathetic poetry, far from the post-war experience, floats away with Arion. To effectively describe the experiences of the modern human is to seek real models – from the present and the past.

Summary: Cultural heritage as a tool of recalling the voice

In his poetry collection, Herbert looks back at the injustice suffered, yet he does not try to forget it. Instead, he records it and attempts to connect the recent war trauma with the universal human experience of conflict and suffering. It must be remarked however, that the poet does not mythicize: the idealization of the suffering for the aesthetic distancing is not ethical and cannot be permitted in modern poetry¹⁶. Herbert treats the classical past with equal irony as his present and its vices¹⁷. For him the concept of balanced classical continuity is unrealistic, but he remains unchangeably attached to the cultural myths, values, and artistic practices: art becomes a way to organize and understand the chaos of history¹⁸. This tendency – the human image against the inevitability of death and existential heroism – was a dominant aspect in Herbert's poetry up to the 1970s¹⁹. And contrary to his assertions about the impossibility of continuing to write poetry shaped on classical models²⁰, the cultural heritage of antiquity remains a permanent point of reference in his works, a compass allowing Herbert to navigate in the new reality.

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¹⁶ Eadem: 80.

¹⁷ Eadem: 75.

¹⁸ Szóstak 2011: 52.

¹⁹ Antoniuk 2009: 456.

²⁰ Popovic 2007: 74-75.

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Abstract

Zbigniew Herbert, one of the most important Polish poets of the 20th century, decided to make his literary debut, titled "String of Light", very late in his life – only at the age of 32, in 1956. This was facilitated not only by the temporarily improved political and cultural situation in post-war Poland, but also by his willingness to talk about the experience of war, which permanently shaped the author and his entire generation. In the collection, Herbert looks back at the injustice suffered, yet he does not try to forget it. Instead, he records it and applies an "antiquity filter", connecting the recent war trauma with the universal human experience of conflict and suffering.

In this paper, I will analyze how Herbert expressed his experiences to process his war trauma. I will discuss selected excerpts from the poems belonging to the collection in terms of the following aspects related to the processing of trauma: the search for lost harmony, the emotions, the critical evaluation of the distant and nearer past, and the attempt to understanding the cruelty.